

Reactions of sulfur(IV) with complex ions of chromium-, manganese-, iron- and cobalt(III) in aqueous medium

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The reactions of sulfur(IV) with complexes of Cr^{III}, Mn^{III}, Fe^{III} and Co^{III} are discussed. Cr^{III} forms O-sulfito complexes while Mn^{III} and Fe^{III} form S-bonded sulfito species. The oxygen bonded sulfito species of Co^{III} are transient intermediates which undergo sulfito ligand linkage isomerization and facile redox reactions. The S-bonded sulfito Co^{III} species can be photochemically isomerized to its O-bonded isomer. The ligand control on the kinetics of reversible substitution of S^{IV} at Cr^{III}, Mn^{III}, Fe^{III} and Co^{III} centres, the redox activities and also the S^{IV} induced reactions of the resulting sulfito complexes are highlighted.

Sulfur is an essential trace element having tremendous biological implications, particularly in the synthesis of essential amino acid cysteine. However, its oxides, SO₂ and SO₃ are toxic and responsible for acid rain and environmental pollution. Also sulfur can exist in oxidation states from -2 to +6 and thus can participate in several metal/nonmetal redox and substitution reactions providing rich chemistry to be explored and exploited. The transition metals and their complexes play important roles as catalysts in several areas of active enzymes and industrial processes¹. In that context there has been great upsurge of interest in recent times on the study of the reactions of sulfur(IV) with several transition metal ions and their complexes². Emphasis has been laid down on the elucidation of metal ion catalyzed autoxidation of SO₂/HSO₃⁻/SO₃²⁻, S^{IV} substitution and S^{IV} induced transformation reactions. Interestingly, the linkage isomerization in HSO₃⁻ and metal sulfito-complexes add further important aspects of both S^{IV} and its metal complexes. A brief review on the reactions of selected metal ions, Cr^{III}, Mn^{III}, Fe^{III} and Co^{III} with sulfur(IV) is presented here.

Sulfur(IV) in aqueous solution

In the gaseous phase sulfur(IV) exists as SO₂. It is fairly soluble in water (94.1 g dm³ mol⁻¹ at 25°, 1 atm pressure)³ and rapidly hydrated and hydrolysed. Several important equilibria are set up when SO₂ dissolves in water,

$$\text{p}K_{1a} = 1.8; \text{p}K_{2a} = 7.2 \quad (25^\circ, I = 0)$$

The bisulfite ion (HSO₃⁻) exists in tautomeric equilibrium

and according to Simons and Waldmann⁴ and Guthrie⁵, the tautomer HO-SO₂ is significantly less favoured in aqueous medium than the corresponding H-SO₃⁻ tautomer. Although Baird and Taylor⁶ suggested that H-S bonded tautomer is energetically favourable, an *ab initio* calculation by Stromberg *et al.*⁷ indicated that HO-SO₂ tautomer is relatively of lower energy than H-SO₃⁻. The existence of H-SO₃⁻ in aqueous solution of bisulfite has been further demonstrated by infrared and Raman spectral measurements ($\nu_{\text{str}}(\text{S-H}) = 2532 \text{ cm}^{-1}$, $\nu_{\text{bending}}(\text{S-H}) = 1128 \text{ cm}^{-1}$)⁸. The S-O band at 730 cm⁻¹ is ascribed to the tautomer HO-SO₂ (Ref. 9). Further details of the spectral identification of the isomeric bisulfite species have been discussed by Connick *et al.*¹⁰ and Stromberg *et al.*⁷.

Dissolved SO₂ (SO₂·H₂O) in aqueous medium is a moderately strong acid due to its ionization to HSO₃⁻, the latter is a much weaker acid (compare values of pK_{1a} and pK_{2a} cited above). The two tautomers of HSO₃⁻ can undergo dimerization (Golding dimer) which ultimately leads to disulfite². The hydrolysis of SO₂ and dimerisation of HSO₃⁻ also attain equilibrium very fast under ambient conditions.

$$k_f = 1.06 \times 10^8 \text{ s}^{-1}; k_r = 2.48 \times 10^8 \text{ dm}^3 \text{ mol}^{-1} \text{ s}^{-1} \\ (24.7^\circ, I = 0.9 \text{ mol dm}^{-3}) \text{ (Ref. 11)}$$

$$k_f = 7 \times 10^2 \text{ dm}^3 \text{ mol}^{-1} \text{ s}^{-1}; k_r = 1.0 \times 10^4 \text{ s}^{-1} \\ (24.7^\circ, I = 0.9 \text{ mol dm}^{-3}) \text{ (Ref. 11)}$$

An *ab initio* calculation on the sulfito and hydrogensulfito

ions (H-SO₂⁻ and HO-SO₂⁻) by Stromberg *et al.*⁷ indicates long S-OH bond (1.716 Å) in HO-SO₂⁻ which is attributed to the fact that the system is assembled from comparatively weakly interacting SO₂ and OH⁻.

Cr^{III}-S^{IV} system :

The hexa-aquachromium(III) ion generally undergoes slow aqua ligand substitution¹². However, the equilibrium between Cr(OH₂)₆³⁺ and HSO₃⁻/SO₃²⁻ is rapidly established and the product is *O*-bonded sulfite complex¹³,

The *cis*- and *trans*-labilizing effect of *O*-bonded sulfite has been reported for some Cr^{III}-sulfite complexes in solution¹³. Marked labilizing effect of sulfite was observed in the aquation of Cr(OH₂)₅Cl²⁺, Cr(OH₂)₅NCS²⁺ and isomeric Cr(OH₂)₄(NCS)₂²⁺. In these reactions it was believed that the reactive species was an *O*-bonded sulfite complex. Carlyle *et al.*¹⁴ further substantiated the suggestions of King *et al.*¹³ that S^{IV} labilization of a ligand at Cr^{III} centre operated through innersphere *O*-bonded sulfite complex. A seven-coordinate transient species (O,O chelated sulfite) was postulated¹⁴ in the sulfite induced acid-catalysed aquation of Cr(OH₂)₅N₃⁺, Cr(OH₂)₅(O₂CCH₃)⁺ and Cr(OH₂)₅(CN)⁺ based on the assumption that Cr^{III} can expand its coordination sphere for this kind of anchimeric assistance.

A detailed study of the kinetics of reversible formation of Cr(OH₂)₅(OSO₂)⁺ has been reported by El-Awady *et al.*¹⁵. They reported a value of (4.4 ± 0.2) × 10² dm³ mol⁻¹ s⁻¹ for the formation of the sulfite complex and 1.58 ± 0.08 dm³ mol⁻¹ s⁻¹ for its acid catalyzed aquation at 25°, *I* = 1.0 mol dm⁻³. Considering the fastness of the reactions, it was presumed that the formation reaction involved addition of SO₂ to Cr^{III}-O bond and H⁺-assisted SO₂ elimination from Cr(OSO₂)⁺ occurred with retention of the Cr^{III}-O bond. Retardation by S₂O₅²⁻ was observed which was explicable in terms of the formation of inert ion-pair, {Cr(OH₂)₅³⁺, S₂O₅²⁻}. They also considered the possibility of the HSO₃⁻ addition to Cr^{III}-O bond via the reaction,

and reported the linkage isomerism of the *O*-bonded sulfite, although Cr^{III} is believed to prefer *O*-bonding,

$$k_{\text{iso}} = (1.98 \pm 0.2) \times 10^{-4} \text{ s}^{-1} \text{ (25}^\circ\text{)}$$

El-Awady *et al.*¹⁵ also reported the synthesis of

Cr(OH₂)₄(OH)(SO₃) without addressing to the bonding mode of sulfite.

The formation of *O*-bonded sulfite complex, (NH₃)₅-CrOSO₂⁺ {λ_{max} (ε_{max}) : 264 (3800); 373 (330); 510 (47)} was reported by van Eldik¹⁶. The reaction involved addition of SO₂ to Cr^{III}-OH with *k* = (2.9 ± 0.6) × 10⁸ dm³ mol⁻¹ s⁻¹ (25°). This complex could not be isolated in the solid state. The dramatic difference in the propensity of Cr(OH₂)₅OH²⁺ and (NH₃)₅CrOH²⁺ towards SO₂ addition may be noted.

The oxygen bonded sulfite complex, *trans*-[(OH₂(Salen)-Cr-OSO₂)⁻, (Salen = *N,N'*-ethylene-bis-salicylidinimate) has been synthesized as its sodium salt and characterized¹⁷. This complex retains its identity in solution at pH >6 but rapidly aquates to its *trans*-(diaqua) congener on acidification. In aqueous solution it is generated in the stopped flow time scale (ms) when *trans*-[(OH₂(Salen)CrOH₂)⁺ is allowed to react with S^{IV} and the mechanism of its formation is consistent with SO₂ addition to Cr^{III}-OH bond.

At 25° (*I* = 0.3 mol dm⁻³) *k*^{SO₂} = (9.2 ± 1.0) × 10⁸ dm³ mol⁻¹ s⁻¹, Δ*H*[‡] = 98 ± 3 kJ mol⁻¹ and Δ*S*[‡] = 256 ± 8 JK⁻¹ mol⁻¹. The large positive value of Δ*S*[‡] is attributed to solvation shell reorganization and solvent structural disorder involved in the process and consequently this is compensated by a relatively large activation enthalpy. There was no evidence of the sulfite ligand linkage isomerism : Cr^{III}-OS₂ → Cr^{III}-SO₃ as reported for Cr(OH₂)₅(OSO₂)⁺. A potentiometric study further indicated that the protonated sulfite complex, *trans*-[(OH₂(Salen)Cr-OSO₂H) (K_d = (1.4 ± 0.5) × 10⁻⁶ mol dm⁻³, 25°, *I* = 0.3 mol dm⁻³) is a stronger acid than HSO₃⁻.

The aqua ligand of *trans*-[(OH₂(Salen)CrOSO₂)⁻ could be replaced by N₃⁻, NCS⁻, pyridine (Py) and imidazole (im) and the corresponding complexes, *trans*-[X(Salen)Cr^{III}(OSO₂)] were isolated as their sodium salts and characterized¹⁷. The formation of these complexes in solution is reversible and both forward and reverse rate constants (*k*_f/*k*_r) have been reported; the values of *k*_r are at least 10³ fold higher than the same for the aquation rate constants of *trans*-[(OH₂/OH)(Salen)CrOH₂]⁺¹⁰ reported by Prasad *et al.*¹⁸. The reaction mechanism is essentially dissociative interchange. A small *trans*-labilizing effect of the *O*-bonded sulfite can not be ruled out. However, there was no *cis*-labilizing effect of the coordinated sulfite in these cases,

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Mn^{III/IV}-S^{IV} system :

The autoxidation of SO₂ to SO₄²⁻ in aqueous medium by water soluble Mn^{II}-phthalocyanine complex, Mn^{II}TSP (TSP = 4,4',4'',4'''-tetrasulphophthalocyanine) has been reported¹⁹. The efficiency of Mn^{II}TSP as a homogeneous catalyst depends upon the stability of (1 : 1) metal-dioxygen adduct.

The Mn^{II}-catalysed autoxidation of HSO₃⁻ at pH 2–4 has been reported by Elding *et al*²⁰. The earlier data for the stability constant of instantaneously formed MnHSO₃⁺ (3 × 10⁴ dm³ mol⁻¹)²¹ have been shown to be erroneous and the reaction scheme for the autoxidation of S^{IV} in the presence of Mn^{II}/Mn^{III} has been modified by Fronaeus *et al*²⁰ to include Mn^{II}-Mn^{III} μ-oxo dimer rather than MnHSO₃⁺ species,

$\beta = [(\text{OH})\text{Mn}^{\text{III}}\text{-O-Mn}^{\text{II}}] / \{\text{Mn}^{\text{III}}\} [\text{Mn}^{\text{II}}] = (3 \pm 1) \times 10^4$ dm³ mol⁻¹ and $k = 1.5 \times 10^6$ dm³ mol⁻¹ s⁻¹ at 25°. The reaction is believed to be initiated by Fe^{III} at 5 × 10⁻⁸ mol dm⁻³. The presence of Fe^{III} in Mn^{II}/HSO₃⁻ system results in a rapid establishment of an iron-manganese redox equilibrium increasing the concentration of Mn^{III} and of the catalysing action of the bridged Mn^{III}/Mn^{II} complex. SO₃⁻ and SO₅⁻ act as chain carriers :

The redox reaction of [Mn^{III}(cdta)]⁻ (cdta⁴⁻ = cyclohexane *N,N,N',N'*-tetraacetate) by S^{IV} has been reported to involve the fast formation of a S^{IV} complex, {Mn^{III}(cdta)(S^{IV})} which undergoes slow internal electron transfer and also further outer-sphere reduction by S^{IV} (Ref. 22). This reaction has been reinvestigated by Chandrawat *et al*²³. Based on the fact that [Mn^{III}(cdta)(OH₂)₂]⁴⁻ is a seven-coordinate complex in which cdta⁴⁻ occupies all six coordination positions of Mn^{III} with H₂O at the seventh coordination site²⁴, they re-defined the reactions as follows :

Values of rate and activation parameters at 25° (*I* = 0.16 mol dm⁻³) are : $k_1 = 22.7 \times 10^4$ dm³ mol⁻¹ s⁻¹, $\Delta H^\ddagger = 48 \pm 1$ kJ mol⁻¹, $\Delta S^\ddagger = 17 \pm 4$ JK⁻¹ mol⁻¹, $k_2 = 10.9 \times 10^4$ dm³ mol⁻¹ s⁻¹, $\Delta H^\ddagger = 38 \pm 3$ kJ mol⁻¹, $\Delta S^\ddagger = 28 \pm 4$ JK⁻¹ mol⁻¹. The value of k_2 compares with that of the rate constant for MnO₄⁻/SO₃²⁻ reaction { $k = 13.3 \times 10^4$ dm³ mol⁻¹ s⁻¹, 25°, *I* = 0.1 mol dm⁻³}²⁵. Chandrawat *et al*²³ suggested outer-sphere mechanism for [Mn^{III}(cdta)(OH₂)₂]⁻ – S^{IV} reaction on the ground that Marcus relationship is obeyed reasonably, assigning the observed deviation in the Marcus plot to the specifics of the complex, [Mn^{III}(cdta)(OH₂)₂]⁻

Mukhopadhyay and Banerjee²⁶ used Mn^{III}(acac)₃ (acac = acetylacetonate) as an oxidizing agent for S^{IV}. The trischelate, however, undergoes hydrolysis to the (diaqua)-bis(acetylacetonato)manganese(III). The diaqua complex forms ion-pairs with HSO₃⁻ and SO₃²⁻. The ion-pairing is governed by H-bonding interactions. Their argument that the rate-determining step involved slow transformation of the outer-sphere ion-pairs to their inner-sphere counterparts and fast electron transfer within the latter species (a case of bonafide substitution controlled redox process) remains to be validated. Although SO₃⁻ was a primary product, its dimerization to dithionate (S₂O₆²⁻) could not be detected thus indicating much faster reduction of Mn^{III} species by this radical.

Recently we investigated the reactions of *trans*-[Mn(Salen)(OH₂)₂]⁺ with S^{IV} (Ref. 27). The reaction occurs in two distinct phases : the initial fast complexation of the Mn^{III} complex by S^{IV}, and a relatively slow reduction of the sulfito complex by S^{IV}. The formation equilibrium constant (*Q*) of the sulfito complex,

has a value (8.91 ± 0.06) × 10² dm³ mol⁻¹ and the molar extinction coefficient of the monosulfito complex at 300 nm is (1.18 ± 0.04) × 10⁴ dm³ mol⁻¹ cm⁻¹. The kinetics of formation of the sulfito complex conform to the following reactions :

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Mono-, bis- and tris(sulfito) complexes of Fe^{III} undergo two successive redox reactions and yield Fe^{II}, SO₄²⁻ and S₂O₆²⁻. The first order rate constants for the first redox step are 0.14, 0.10 and 0.055 s⁻¹ (pH = 2.5, 25°, Ref. 30) for tris-, bis- and mono(sulfito)iron(III) species, respectively. The second redox step has a rate constant of 0.01 s⁻¹ (25°) and it exhibits only slight pH dependence. The pH dependence was interpreted by them in terms of two stage protonation equilibria of Fe^{III}(SO₃)₃:

The electron transfer between tris(1,10-phenanthroline)iron(III) and S^{IV} (Ref. 31) obeyed the stoichiometry,

and the rate law,

$$-\partial[\text{FeL}_3^{3+}]_{\text{T}}/\partial t = (k_1 + k_2/[\text{H}^+] + k_3[\text{HSO}_3^-])[\text{HSO}_3^-][\text{FeL}_3^{3+}]$$

HSO₃⁻, SO₃²⁻ and S₂O₅²⁻ are the reactive S^{IV} species for which the rate constants are k₁, k₂ and k₃, respectively. Lack of evidence for dithionate ion as a product suggested that SO₃²⁻ is scavenged by FeL₃³⁺. Also there was no evidence of sulfonation of the coordinated orthophenanthroline in the process. The electron transfer is outer-sphere type and the rate and activation parameters are: k₁ = 20 dm³ mol⁻¹ s⁻¹, ΔH[‡] = 40.6 ± 2.9 kJ mol⁻¹, ΔS[‡] = -84 ± 12 JK⁻¹ mol⁻¹; k₂ = 4.2 dm³ mol⁻¹ s⁻¹, ΔH[‡] = 31.0 ± 3.7 kJ mol⁻¹, ΔS[‡] = -130 ± 12 JK⁻¹ mol⁻¹; k₃ = 7200 dm³ mol⁻¹ s⁻¹, ΔH[‡] = 58.6 ± 4.2 kJ mol⁻¹, ΔS[‡] = 25 ± 16 JK⁻¹ mol⁻¹ (25°, I = 1.0 mol dm⁻³)(Ref. 31).

The reaction of SO₃²⁻ with [Fe(edta)(OH₂)]⁻ is fast and the product has been identified as the S-bonded sulfito complex, [Fe(edta)(SO₃)]³⁻ (ε = 380 dm³ mol⁻¹ cm⁻¹ at pH = 7.2; ν(S-O stretch) 1093 cm⁻¹)³². The equilibrium constant (K^{SO₃}) for the formation of the sulfito complex is 6.2 ± 0.3 dm³ mol⁻¹ (25°, I = 0.5 mol dm⁻³),

The kinetics of formation of the sulfito complex (k_{formation} = 4 × 10⁶ dm³ mol⁻¹ s⁻¹, 25°, pH = 7.3, I = 0.5 mol dm⁻³, 25°) is believed to follow a D mechanism and the limiting water dissociation rate constant for [Fe(edta)OH₂]⁻ attained

at high [SO₃²⁻]_T has been calculated by van Eldik *et al*³² to be 6.3 × 10⁴ s⁻¹ at pH = 7.3 and 25°. This value when extrapolated to lower pH from a pH dependence study yields 1.8 × 10⁵ s⁻¹ for the water exchange rate constant of the aqua complex which is close to the value (8 × 10⁵ s⁻¹) obtained from NMR measurements³³.

The kinetics of S^{IV} anation of [Fe(TetrenH₂)(OH₂)₃]⁵⁺ (tetrenH₂ = N,N'-diprotonated tetraethylenepentamine) and subsequent slow reduction of [Fe(TetrenH₂)(SO₃)]³⁺ was recently reported by us³⁴ in order to examine the 'multidentate' effect if any. The anation reaction is reversible and follows ion-pair mechanism with interchange dissociative mode of activation,

with Q = 20.3 ± 2.6 dm³ mol⁻¹, k_f = 71 ± 10 s⁻¹, ΔH[‡] = 67 ± 2 kJ mol⁻¹, ΔS[‡] = 14 ± 7 JK⁻¹ mol⁻¹; k_r = 4.1 ± 0.4 s⁻¹, ΔH[‡] = 38 ± 7 kJ mol⁻¹, ΔS[‡] = 104 ± 26 JK⁻¹ mol⁻¹ (25°, I = 0.5 mol dm⁻³)(Ref. 34).

The internal reduction of the product sulfito complex displayed biphasic kinetics characteristics of its existence in two isomeric forms differing in reactivity (k_{fast}/k_{slow} = 10, k_{fast} = 2.7 × 10⁻⁴ s⁻¹ at 40°, I = 0.5 mol dm⁻³). The formation of S₂O₆²⁻ due to dimerization of SO₃²⁻ on a competitive scale was also observed and the overall stoichiometry for reduction was sensitive to pH.

The study of ligand control on the formation and reduction of iron(III)-sulfito complexes was extended by us to *trans*-[Fe(Salen)(OH₂)₂]⁺ (Ref. 35), [Fe(ida)(OH₂)₃]⁺ (Ref. 36) (ida = iminodiacetate). Both the aqua/aqua-hydroxo complexes undergo fast complexation with S^{IV} species (HSO₃⁻, SO₃²⁻) followed by slow reduction of the sulfito complexes. While the *trans*-[Fe(Salen)(OH₂)₂]⁺ forms only one isomeric sulfito species, *trans*-[(OH₂)Fe(Salen)(SO₃)]⁻, both mono- and disulfito complexes, [Fe(ida)(OH₂)₂(SO₃)]⁻ and [Fe(ida)(OH₂)(SO₃)₂]³⁻ have been identified by stopped flow and rapid scan spectroscopic measurements. The internal reduction of the disulfito complex also displayed biphasic kinetics, attributed to different reactivities of the two isomers (i.e. *cis*- and *trans*-disulfito complexes); the dimerisation of SO₃²⁻ to S₂O₆²⁻ occurred irrespective of the primary ligand. A comparison of the second order rate constant for the formation of monosulfito complexes,

will be pertinent here. Values of k ($\text{dm}^3 \text{ mol}^{-1} \text{ s}^{-1}$, 25°) are 2.7×10^2 (HSO_3^- , $I = 1.0 \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$; Ref. 37), 6×10^3 (HSO_3^- , $I = 0.5 \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$), 4.3×10^6 (SO_3^{2-} , $I = 0.5 \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$) and 1.44×10^3 ($I = 0.5 \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$) for $\text{L} = \text{H}_2\text{O}$ ($n = 1$), *ida* ($n = 3$), *edta* ($n = 5$) and *TetrenH* $_2^{2+}$ ($n = 3$), respectively. The trend in the substitutional lability of the aqua complexes $\text{Fe}(\text{OH}_2)_6^{3+} < \text{Fe}(\text{TetrenH}_2)(\text{OH}_2)_5^{3+} < \text{Fe}(\text{ida})(\text{OH}_2)_3^+ \ll \text{Fe}(\text{edta})(\text{OH}_2)_2^-$ points out that the primary ligands in the coordination sphere of iron(III) play a significant role in mediating the rate of H_2O substitution by S^{IV} . This must be related to the electron displacement properties and steric effects of the ligands favouring interchange dissociative mode of activation. The electrostatic control of overall charges of the complexes and S^{IV} species are of minor significance. The observed redox activities of $\text{Fe}^{\text{III}}\text{L}(\text{SO}_3)_n$ species are in line with the expected reduction potential changes of $\text{Fe}^{\text{III}}/\text{Fe}^{\text{II}}$ system on complexation.

It is of interest to note that in none of the cases cited above there was evidence in favour of the oxygen bonded sulfite complex of iron(III). Johnson and Bernard³⁸, however, in a recent study of the oxidation of S^{IV} by ferrate suggested the formation of an oxygen bonded S^{IV} species of Fe^{VI} as a transient reactive intermediate,

which further conforms to the stoichiometry,

and the rate law,

$$-\partial\text{Fe}^{\text{VI}}/\partial t = k^{\text{SO}_2}[\text{FeO}_4^{2-}][\text{SO}_3^{2-}][\text{H}^+] \quad (24)$$

The decomposition of the *O*-bonded sulfiteiron(VI) species is rate-limiting in this two-electron (inner-sphere) electron transfer step. The *O*-bonded sulfite species, $\text{O}_3\text{Fe-O-SO}_3\text{H}^{3-}$ postulated as a kinetic entry awaits further experimentation for verification. The work of Johnson and Bernard is an improvement on that of Goff and Murman³⁹ who proposed the rate law as : $\text{rate} = k[\text{FeO}_4^{2-}][\text{SO}_3^{2-}]$. However, the reaction scheme proposed by Johnson and Bernard is consistent with the results of O^{18} enrichment in the product SO_4^{2-}

reported by Goff and Murman.

Cobalt(II/III)-S^{IV} system :

Catalysis of oxidation of aqueous SO_2 by a Co^{II} -phthalocyanine complex, CoTPS^{2-} ($\text{TPS} = 4,4',4'',4'''$ -tetrasulphophthalocyanine) has been reported¹⁹. Michaelis-Menten kinetics expression based on a bisubstrate kinetic model was used to interpret the rate data. The central metal ion has been varied and the sequence of reactivity with respect to metal ion ($\text{Co}^{\text{II}} > \text{Fe}^{\text{II}} > \text{Mn}^{\text{II}} > \text{V}^{\text{IV}} \sim \text{Ni}^{\text{II}} \sim \text{Cu}^{\text{II}}$) is believed to reflect relative efficiency of the square-planar transition metal complexes to bind O_2 .

The *S*-bonded sulfite in several sulfite complexes of cobalt(III) has been reported to exert marked *trans*-labilizing influence⁴⁰. The evidences for *trans*-effect have been deduced from both synthetic strategy as well as kinetic consequences. The enhanced substitution rate of a ligand *trans* to SO_3^{2-} in a cobalt(III)-sulfite complex (*S*-bonded) has led to the belief that the *S*-bonded sulfite favours SN_1 limiting (*D*) mechanism of ligand substitution at cobalt(III) centre. Richards and Halpern⁴¹ elegantly demonstrated the *trans*-effect of SO_3^{2-} in $[(\text{NH}_3)_5\text{Co-SO}_3]^+$ and *cis*- $[\text{Co}(\text{NH}_3)_4(\text{SO}_3)_2]^-$ by ammonia exchange experiments in which NH_3 *trans* to SO_3^{2-} (1 NH_3 for mono- and 2 NH_3 for the disulfite complexes) exchanged rapidly with $^{15}\text{NH}_3$.

The structural *trans*-effect (STE) has been demonstrated for $(\text{NH}_3)_5\text{CoSO}_3^+$, *trans*- $[(\text{OH}_2)\text{Co}(\text{en})_2(\text{SO}_3)]^+$ etc. showing long Co-L bond *trans* to SO_3^{2-} (Table 1).

Table 1. Structural *trans*-effect in some sulfite complexes of cobalt(III)

Compd.	r(Co-L), Å		Ref.
	<i>trans</i> to SO_3	<i>cis</i> to SO_3	
$(\text{NH}_3)_5\text{Co-SO}_3^+$	2.055	1.966	2 218 a
<i>trans</i> - $[(\text{SO}_3)(\text{en})_2\text{Co}(\text{imidazole})]^+$	2.008	1.963	2.223 a
<i>cis</i> - $[(\text{SO}_3)_2\text{Co}(\text{NH}_3)_4]^-$	1.993	2.224	a
	2.023	1.970	2.221
<i>trans</i> - $[(\text{SO}_3)(\text{en})_2\text{CoOH}_2]^+$	2.037	1.942	2.181 a

^aSee Table 4 of Ref. : C. L. Ratson, A. H White and J. K. Yandell, *Aust. J. Chem.*, 1978, 31, 993

The *trans*-effect of *S*-bonded sulfite is responsible for the stereochemical change : $(\alpha\beta\text{S})(\text{Tetren})\text{Co-SO}_3^+ \rightarrow (\alpha\alpha\text{R})(\text{Tetren})\text{Co-SO}_3^+$ (Ref. 42) despite the robust and 'multidentate' ligand environment of cobalt. The self-decomposition of peroxyxynitrite in alkaline medium ($2 \text{O}=\text{N}-\text{O}-\text{O}^- \rightarrow \text{O}_2 + 2\text{NO}_2^-$) is reported to be strongly catalyzed by sulfite

cobalt(III) complexes, $(\text{NH}_3)_5\text{Co-SO}_3^+$ and $\text{cis}-(\text{NH}_3)_4-(\text{SO}_3)_2^-$. The catalytic effect is exclusively due to the *trans*-effect of the sulfite ligand which favours rapid loss of the NH_3 moiety *trans* to SO_3^{2-} followed by generation of the active peroxyxynitrocobalt(III) species by incorporation of $\text{O}=\text{N-O-O}^-$ (Ref. 43).

The oxygen-bonded sulfite complexes of cobalt(III) have been reported as transient intermediates⁴⁴⁻⁴⁹ in the reactions of aqua-aminocobalt(III) complexes with an equilib-

Table 2. UV-visible spectral data for some *O*- and *S*-bonded sulfite complexes of cobalt(III)

Compd	λ_{max} , nm	ϵ , $\text{dm}^3 \text{mol}^{-1} \text{cm}^{-1}$	Ref
$(\text{NH}_3)_5\text{CoOSO}_2^+$	518, 330	88, 2100	44
$(\text{NH}_3)_5\text{Co-SO}_3^+$	456	150	44
	457, 278	148, 17800	<i>a</i>
	456, 278	150, 18900	40g
<i>trans</i> -(NH_3) ₄ (CN)(OSO ₂)	458, 318	100, 1800	45
<i>trans</i> -(NH_3) ₄ Co(CN)(SO ₃)	427, 278	150, 19500	45
(tetren)Co-OSO ₂ ⁺	510, 330	150, 1928	46
(tetren)Co-SO ₃ ⁺	444, 281	236, 16900	46
<i>cis</i> [Co(en) ₂ (RNH ₂)(OSO ₂) ⁺] RNH ₂ =			
NH ₃	510, 330	127, 2000	47
MeNH ₂	510, 330	115, 1663	47
EtNH ₂	510, 330	120, 2132	47
C ₆ H ₅ CH ₂ NH ₂	510, 330	110, 1670	47
C ₆ H ₁₁ NH ₂	510, 330	105, 1677	47
<i>N</i> -Meimidazole	500, 340	117, 2360	48
Imidazole	510, 340	127, 2197	48
Benzimidazole	515, 345	123, 2450	48
<i>trans</i> -[Co(en) ₂ (OH ₂)(SO ₃) ⁺]	466, 274	160, 1600	40f
<i>trans</i> -[Co(tn) ₂ (OH ₂)(SO ₃) ⁺]	475, 280	180, 1100	40f

^aH Siebert and G Witke. *Z Anorg Allgem Chem*, 1973, 399, 43

rium mixture of $\text{SO}_2/\text{HSO}_3^-/\text{SO}_3^{2-}$. This species is reversibly formed by the reaction,

where L is a pentadentate amine ligand or comprises ligands with several *N*-donor functions of lower denticity. The *O*-bonded sulfite complexes have eluded isolation in solid state but have been characterized in solution by uv-visible spectroscopy (Table 2) and by their chemical reactivities. The extremely high values of the formation/dissociation rate constants ($k_f \sim 10^8 \text{ dm}^3 \text{ mol}^{-1} \text{ s}^{-1}$, $k_r \sim 10^6 \text{ dm}^3 \text{ mol}^{-1} \text{ s}^{-1}$, 25°, $I = 1.0 \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$; Table 3) in contrast with slow ligand

substitution rates of octahedral cobalt(III) complexes¹² have led to the belief that the reaction involves rate-limiting addition of SO_2 to $\text{Co}^{\text{III}}-\text{OH}$ in which Co-O bond is fully retained. The microscopic reversibility demands that Co-O bond is retained in the acid catalyzed decomposition reaction also. Hence the formation/decomposition of the sulfite complex attains a transition state which resembles substitution at S^{IV} centre. This mechanism was further supported by the ¹⁷O exchange study on $(\text{NH}_3)_5\text{Co-OSO}_2^+$ (Ref. 50) in which it was shown that $(\text{NH}_3)_5\text{Co}^{\text{III-17}}\text{OH}_2$ bond remained in tact during both formation and acid catalyzed dissociation of the *O*-sulfite complex. Also this study established that oxygen scrambling in the bonded sulfite did not occur during the process :

However, subsequent slow internal reduction of cobalt(III) by the bound sulfite transfers ¹⁷O labeling to the product $\text{HSO}_4^-/\text{SO}_4^{2-}$.

A comprehensive scheme valid for the reactions of some aqua-aminocobalt(III) complexes with S^{IV} is presented below :

The dimerization of SO_3^* in these reactions could not be detected. The sulfite ligand linkage isomerization is synchronous with the loss of RNH_2 and *cis-trans* isomerization. This process is also influenced by steric effect of the departing amine (RNH_2), i.e. k_{iso} increased with increasing steric bulk of group R. This has been attributed to a special *cis*-effect of the *O*-bonded sulfite^{47,48}. In basic medium, the *O*-sulfite complex does not undergo reduction but base-catalyzed isomerization and hydrolysis are the two main reactions which follow

A rate comparison for different reactions of some *O*-sulfito complexes of cobalt(III) is presented in Table 3.

spending *trans*-isomer ($k_{\text{iso}} = 1.56 \times 10^{-3} \text{ s}^{-1}$ at 25°) with 3.5/96.5 *cis/trans* isomer distribution at equilibrium.

The direct S^{IV} substitution at cobalt(III) centre favouring *S*-bonded sulfito complexes in absence of *trans*-effect of *S*-bonded sulfite has also been reported. In basic medium (pH >10), the reaction of (tetren)CoOH²⁺ with SO₃²⁻ results in the formation of (tetren)Co-SO₃⁺ (Ref. 54). The formation of *cis*-[Co(AA)₂(OH₂)(SO₃)]⁺ and *cis*-[Co(AA)₂(SO₃)₂]⁻ (AA = dipyridyl and 1,10-phenanthroline) without the intervention of the corresponding *O*-bonded sulfito complexes has also been reported⁵⁵. The sulfite substitution reaction

Table 3. Ligand effects on the formation (k_f), acid-catalysed aquation (k_r), isomerization (k_{iso}), internal reduction (k_{red}) and base hydrolysis (k_b) of some *cis*-[(en)₂Co(RNH₂)(OSO₂)]⁺

RNH ₂	10 ⁻⁸ k_f^a	10 ⁻⁶ k_r^a	10 ⁴ k_{red}^a	10 ⁴ k_{iso}^a	10 ⁴ k_b^a	
	(25°)	(25°)	(35°)	spontaneous (35°)	base-catalysed (25°)	
NH ₃ ^b	4.7 ± 0.4	17.2 ± 1.5	~0.11	0.53	23 ± 2	14 ± 1
Me ^b	2.4 ± 0.3	11.8 ± 1.9	0.57 ± 0.03	0.9 ± 0.1	29 ± 3	16 ± 1
Et ^b	4.8 ± 0.5	9.1 ± 1.0	1.0 ± 0.1	1.3 ± 0.2	35 ± 4	9 ± 4
PhCH ₂ NH ₂ ^b	2.5 ± 0.2	1.7 ± 0.4	2.7 ± 0.2	2.9 ± 0.3	18 ± 6	8 ± 2
C ₆ H ₁₁ ^b	2.0 ± 0.1	3.0 ± 0.3	2.8 ± 0.2	3.6 ± 0.8	86 ± 8	111 ± 13
Imidazole ^{c,d}	0.77 ± 0.03	2.66 ± 0.26	~0.04	~0.2	9.6 ± 0.1	3.1 ± 0.2
Benzimidazole ^d	1.3 ± 0.09	3.5 ± 0.4	0.4 ± 0.06	10.8 ± 0.4	21 ± 3	13 ± 2
<i>N</i> -Meimidazole ^d	2.1 ± 0.1	4.3 ± 0.2	0.06 ± 0.01	1.7 ± 0.2	19 ± 2	23 ± 2
	1.04 ± 0.07 ^e	2.5 ± 0.3 ^e		16.0 ± 4.0 ^{e,f}		
	4.7 ± 0.3 ^g	2.2 ± 0.4 ^{g,h}	140 ± 30 ^g			

^aUnits: dm³ mol⁻¹ s⁻¹ for k_f , k_r , k_{iso} (base-catalysed) and k_b ; s⁻¹ for k_{red} and k_{iso} (spontaneous), $l = 1.0 \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$, ^b Ref. 47; ^cA. N. Acharya and A. C. Dash. *Proc. Indian Acad. Sci. (Chem. Sci.)*, 1993, **105**, 225. ^dRef. 48; may be noted that the coordinated imidazole and benzimidazole exist in the N-H deprotonated form in basic medium (pH >10); ^{e,f} for *trans*-(CN)(NH₃)₄Co(OSO₂), Ref 45, k_{iso} at 40°; ^{g,h} for (NH₃)₅Co(OSO₂)⁺, Ref. 44, k_r at 10°.

The ligand control on the isomerization, redox and base-catalysed hydrolysis (S_N1CB) of *O*-sulfito complexes is substantial rather than on the formation/dissociation of such species (Table 3). The 10³-fold rate enhancement by the anionic micelles of sodium dodecyl sulfate⁵¹ in the sulfite ligand linkage isomerization: (tetren)Co-OSO₂⁺ → (tetren)Co-SO₃⁺ and pronounced acceleration of the rate of intramolecular electron transfer: (NH₃)₅Co^{III}-OS^{IV}O₂⁺ → (NH₃)₅-Co^{II}-OS^VO₂⁺ and H⁺-catalyzed aquation of Co(tetren)-(OSO₂)⁺ by the reaction media (varied by water + organic cosolvents)⁵² are explicable in terms of both electrostatic and non-electrostatic medium effects (hydrophobicity and solvent structure).

Jackson⁵³ was able to synthesise *cis*-[Co(en)₂(OH₂)(SO₃)]⁺ (*S*-bonded isomer) by the nitrosation reaction of *cis*-[Co(en)₂(OH₂)N₃]²⁺ followed by fast capture of the five-coordinate intermediate by SO₃²⁻/HSO₃⁻. The *cis*-(aquo)-(sulfito) complex, however, rapidly isomerized to the corre-

of the diaqua complexes was too fast to be followed by stopped flow spectrometry, only the transformation of the (aqua)(sulfito) complex to the disulfito analogs was followed (ms time-scale). The redox behaviour of these sulfito complexes was, however, quite normal { $k_{\text{red}} = (1.18 \pm 0.05) \times 10^{-4} \text{ s}^{-1}$ and $(0.83 \pm 0.07) \times 10^{-4} \text{ s}^{-1}$ at 45° for *cis*-[(phen)₂Co(SO₃H)(SO₃)] and *cis*-[(bipy)₂Co(SO₃H)(SO₃)] respectively}⁵⁵.

Although the formation of *O*-bonded sulfito complexes has been established beyond doubt in the S^{IV} substitution reactions (via rate-limiting SO₂ addition to Co^{III}-OH), a contrasting feature was evident in the reaction of *trans*-[(Salen)Co(OH₂)₂]⁺ (Ref. 56). The reaction, over a wide pH range (pH = 3–8) and [S^{IV}]_T obeyed the characteristic features of SO₂ addition to Co^{III}-OH but the product was the *S*-bonded sulfito complex, *trans*-[Co(Salen)(OH₂)(SO₃)]⁻; a concerted process in which Co-sulfur bond formation and Co-O bond breaking are synchronized with SO₂

addition to Co^{III}-OH was proposed.

Some of the *S*-bonded sulfitecobalt(III) species can be photochemically isomerized to their *O*-bonded sulfite analog under flash photolytic (μ s time-scale) conditions. Prolonged exposure to UV-radiation (253.7 nm), however, results in both photoreduction and aquation. The rates of photochemical sulfite ligand linkage isomerization of *trans*-[Co(AA)₂(OH)₂(SO₃-S)]⁺ {AA = en(1,2-diaminoethane); tn(1,3-diaminopropane)} do not display significant chelate ring size effect :

On the contrary, multiple chelate rings around cobalt(III) appear to retard this photochemical linkage isomerization⁵⁷,

Further work need to be done on the role of chelation and stereochemical effects on kinetics and mechanism of photoisomerization of the *S*-bonded sulfite complexes not only of cobalt(III) but of several other metal ions not prone to S^{IV} reduction.

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References

- 1 R. H. Holm, P. Kennepohl and E. I. Solomon, *Chem. Rev.*, 1996, **96**, 2236, and references cited therein.
- 2 C. Brandt and R. van Eldik, *Chem. Rev.*, 1995, **95**, 119.

3. See Table 2.1 of Ref. 2.
- 4 A. Simon and K. Waldmann, *Z. Anorg. Allg. Chem.*, 1955, **231**, 135.
- 5 J. P. Guthrie, *Can. J. Chem.*, 1970, **57**, 454.
- 6 N. C. Baird and K. F. Taylor, *J. Comput. Chem.*, 1981, **2**, 225.
- 7 A. Stromberg, O. Gropen, V. Wahlgren and O. Lindqvist, *Inorg. Chem.*, 1983, **22**, 1129.
- 8 A. Simon and W. Schmidt, *Z. Electrochem.*, 1960, **64**, 737.
- 9 B. Meyer, I. Peter and C. Rosenlund, *Spectrochim. Acta, Part A*, 1979, **35**, 345.
- 10 R. E. Connick, T. M. Tam and E. V. Deuster, *Inorg. Chem.*, 1982, **21**, 103.
- 11 R. H. Betts and R. H. Voss, *Can. J. Chem.*, 1970, **48**, 2035.
- 12 F. Basolo and R. G. Pearson, "Mechanisms of Inorganic Reactions", 2nd. ed., Wiley, New York, 1967; C. H. Langford and H. B. Gray, "Ligand Substitution Processes", Benjamin, New York, 1966.
- 13 D. W. Carlyle and E. L. King, *Inorg. Chem.*, 1970, **9**, 2333.
- 14 S. N. Choi and D. W. Carlyle, *Inorg. Chem.*, 1974, **13**, 1027.
- 15 P. A. Moritzen, A. A. El-Awady and G. M. Harris, *Inorg. Chem.*, 1985, **24**, 313.
- 16 R. van Eldik, *Inorg. Chim. Acta*, 1980, **42**, 49.
- 17 A. C. Dash, A. N. Acharya, P. Mohanty and A. Das, *Int. J. Chem. Kinet.*, 1998, **30**, 373.
- 18 D. R. Prasad, T. Ramasami, D. Ramaswamy and M. Santappa, *Inorg. Chem.*, 1981, **21**, 850.
- 19 S. D. Boyce, M. R. Hoffman, P. A. Hong and L. M. Moberly, *Environ. Sci. Technol.*, 1983, **17**, 602.
- 20 S. Fronaeus, J. Berglund and L. I. Elding, *Inorg. Chem.*, 1998, **37**, 4939.
- 21 J. Berglund, S. Fronaeus and L. I. Elding, *Inorg. Chem.*, 1993, **12**, 4527.
- 22 V. M. Bobba, G. Giraudi and E. Mentasti, *Transition Met. Chem.*, 1988, **13**, 256.
- 23 U. Chandrawat, A. Prakash and R. N. Mehrotra, *Can. J. Chem.*, 1992, **73**, 1531.
- 24 R. E. Hamm and M. A. Suwyn, *Inorg. Chem.*, 1967, **6**, 139; D. H. Macartney and D. W. Thompson, *Inorg. Chem.*, 1989, **28**, 2195.
- 25 J. L. Simandi, M. Jakey, C. A. Savage and Z. A. Schelly, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 1985, **107**, 4220.
- 26 S. Mukhopadhyay and R. N. Banerjee, *J. Chem. Soc., Dalton Trans.*, 1993, 933.
- 27 A. C. Dash and A. Das, *Int. J. Chem. Kinet.*, 1999, **31**, 627.
- 28 (a) C. Brandt, I. Fabian and R. van Eldik, *Inorg. Chem.*, 1994, **33**, 687; (b) C. Brandt and R. van Eldik, *Transition Met. Chem.*, 1998, **23**, 667.
- 29 F. F. Prinsloo, C. Brandt, V. Lipentsiotis, J. J. Picnarr and R. van Eldik, *Inorg. Chem.*, 1997, **36**, 119.
- 30 J. Kraft and R. van Eldik, *Inorg. Chem.*, 1989, **28**, 2307.
- 31 D. W. Carlyle, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 1972, **94**, 3525.

32. M. D. Ritter and R. van Eldik, *J. Chem. Soc., Dalton Trans.*, 1992, 1037.
33. J. Bloch and G. Navon, *J. Inorg. Nucl. Chem.*, 1980, **42**, 693.
34. A. C. Dash, A. K. Patnaik and N. Das, *Indian J. Chem., Sect. A*, 1998, **36**, 268.
35. A. Das and A. C. Dash, *Inorg. React. Mechanisms*, 2000, **2**, 101.
36. A. C. Dash, K. C. Jena and A. Das, *Indian J. Chem., Sect. A*, 1999, **38**, 670.
37. D. W. Carlyle, *Inorg. Chem.*, 1973, **10**, 761.
38. M. D. Johnson and J. Bernard, *Inorg. Chem.*, 1992, **31**, 5140.
39. H. Goff and R. K. Murman, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 1971, **93**, 6058.
40. (a) J. E. Byrd and W. K. Wilmarth, *Inorg. Chim. Acta Rev.*, 1971, **5**, 7; (b) J. Halpern, R. A. Palmer and L. M. Blakely, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 1960, **88**, 2877; (c) G. Tsiang and W. K. Wilmarth, *Inorg. Chem.*, 1968, **7**, 2535; (d) D. R. Stranks and J. K. Yandell, *Inorg. Chem.*, 1970, **9**, 751; (e) J. K. Yandell and L. A. Tomlins, *Aust. J. Chem.*, 1978, **31**, 365; (f) A. C. Dash, K. C. Jena, A. Roy, D. Mukherjee and S. Aditya, *J. Chem. Soc., Dalton Trans.*, 1997, 2451; (g) R. C. Elder, M. J. Heeg, M. D. Payne, M. Trukla and E. Deutsch, *Inorg. Chem.*, 1978, **17**, 4315.
41. L. Richards and J. Halpern, *Inorg. Chem.*, 1976, **15**, 2511.
42. K. J. Schneider, R. van Eldik, A. Roodt and J. G. Leipoldt, *Inorg. Chim. Acta*, 1986, **122**, 1.
43. A. M. Al-Ajlouni, P. C. Paul and E. S. Gould, *Inorg. Chem.*, 1998, **37**, 1435.
44. R. van Eldik and G. M. Harris, *Inorg. Chem.*, 1980, **19**, 880.
45. J. Kraft and R. van Eldik, *Inorg. Chem.*, 1985, **24**, 3391.
46. A. C. Dash, A. A. El-Awady and G. M. Harris, *Inorg. Chem.*, 1981, **20**, 3160.
47. A. C. Dash and K. C. Jena, *Transition Met. Chem.*, 1997, **22**, 141.
48. A. C. Dash, A. K. Patnaik and A. N. Acharya, *Transition Met. Chem.*, 1998, **23**, 45.
49. A. A. El-Awady and G. M. Harris, *Inorg. Chem.*, 1986, **25**, 1323.
50. R. van Eldik, J. V. Jouanne and H. Kelm, *Inorg. Chem.*, 1982, **21**, 2818.
51. A. C. Dash and A. K. Patnaik, *J. Chem. Res. (S)*, 1995, 230; *J. Chem. Res. (M)*, 1995, 1529.
52. A. C. Dash, A. K. Patnaik and G. S. Bramha, *Indian J. Chem., Sect. A*, 1997, **36**, 260; A. C. Dash, N. M. Dash, S. Aditya and A. Roy, *Indian J. Chem., Sect. A*, 1988, **27**, 398.
53. W. G. Jackson, *Inorg. Chem.*, 1988, **27**, 777.
54. A. C. Dash, A. N. Acharya and A. K. Patnaik, *Proc. Indian Acad. Sci. (Chem. Sci.)*, 1995, **107**, 533.
55. V. K. Johsi, R. van Eldik and G. M. Harris, *Inorg. Chem.*, 1986, **25**, 2229.
56. A. Das and A. C. Dash, *J. Chem. Soc., Dalton Trans.*, 2000, 1949.
57. A. C. Dash, K. C. Jena and A. Das, *Indian J. Chem., Sect. A*, 1999, **38**, 660.